

National Leprosy Conference 2025

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Abstract Book

PP-1: Strengthening the Mechanism for Historical Contact Tracing of Leprosy Patients in the Colombo Regional Director of Health Services Area

Liyanage ADMD¹, Sumal Nandasena², Gajanayake C¹, Rekanjalee Edirisinghe¹, Muthahhara M¹, Viraj Udayanga¹, Nafrees MMM¹

¹Office of the Regional Director of Health Services Colombo, ²Office of the Provincial Director of Health Services, Western Province

Background

Leprosy is a chronic communicable disease with an incubation period potentially extending to many years. Therefore, screening of contacts of index patients at regular intervals after the first encounter is a strategy employed to prevent disease transmission. In-line with the National programme, contacts of leprosy patients diagnosed from 2016 to 2020 are currently being traced and screened in the Colombo RDHS area with this initiative.

Description of the Intervention/Initiative

A methodical approach was introduced to streamline historical contact tracing at district level and linked to the existing monitoring mechanism of leprosy patients. Each Medical Officer of Health (MOH) area has a separate Google Sheet which is accessible and editable at both MOH-level and district level. Details of all patients diagnosed from 2016 to 2020 were extracted from the district leprosy registers MOH-wise and entered into these Google Sheets. A separate tab was maintained for each year (2016-2020). The respective MOHs had access to data that were only relevant to them.

Methods Used for the Evaluation

Qualitative feedback from MOH staff revealed how the initiative decreased the time and effort required on their end to identify these patients using their own paper-based records. Number of index patients traced, number of contacts identified and screened were compared to figures of the previous year. The progress of this initiative is being monitored in frequent epidemiological meetings that are done both physically and remotely. Additionally an indicator was added to the annual appraisal program of Colombo RDHS area on the success of this process.

Results

The initiative facilitated monitoring of historical contact tracing. A total of 1115 index patients were identified for the period 2016-2020. Historical contact tracing is carried out in all MOH areas. Within a month of implementing this initiative nearly 100 index patients were traced and 300 contacts were identified. In comparison to previous years, the number of historical contacts that can be potentially traced and screened by the end of this year is seemingly considerably high with this initiative.

Lessons Learnt

Proactive initiatives to streamline and monitor special activities like historical contact tracing give it due weight and motivate the MOH-level staff. Employing open-source digital resources like Google Sheets for implementation increases efficiency and helps reduce the burden at ground level.